
LEADOR: A Method for End-to-End Participatory Design of Autonomous Social Robots

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Participatory Design has been used to good success in Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), but
4 typically remains limited to the early phases of development, with subsequent robot behaviours
5 then being hardcoded by engineers or utilised in Wizard-of-Oz (WoZ) systems that rarely achieve
6 autonomy. In this article, we present LEADOR (Led-by-Experts Automation and Design Of Robots)
7 an *end-to-end* participatory design (PD) methodology for domain expert co-design, automation
8 and evaluation of social robot behaviour. This method starts with typical PD, working with the
9 domain expert(s) to co-design the interaction specifications and state and action space of the
10 robot. It then replaces the traditional offline programming or WoZ phase by an in-situ and online
11 teaching phase where the domain expert can live-program or teach the robot how to behave
12 while being embedded in the interaction context. We believe that this live teaching phase can
13 be best achieved by adding a learning component to a WoZ setup, which captures experts'
14 implicit knowledge, as they intuitively respond to the dynamics of the situation. The robot then
15 progressively learns an appropriate, expert-approved policy, ultimately leading to full autonomy,
16 even in sensitive and/or ill-defined environments. However, LEADOR is agnostic to the exact
17 technical approach used to facilitate this learning process. The extensive inclusion of the domain
18 expert(s) in robot design represents established responsible innovation practice, lending credibility
19 to the system both during the teaching phase and when operating autonomously. The combination
20 of this expert inclusion with the focus on in-situ development also means LEADOR supports a
21 mutual shaping approach to social robotics. We draw on two previously published, foundational
22 works from which this (generalisable) methodology has been derived in order to demonstrate the
23 feasibility and worth of this approach, provide concrete examples in its application and identify
24 limitations and opportunities when applying this framework in new environments.

1 INTRODUCTION

25 In the context of robotics research, participatory design attempts to empower non-roboticists such that
26 they can shape the direction of robotics research and actively collaborate in robot design (Lee et al., 2017).
27 Typically, participatory design is achieved by researchers running workshops or focus groups with end-users
28 and/or domain experts. Output may include potential use case scenarios (Jenkins and Draper, 2015), design
29 guidelines/ recommendations (Winkle et al., 2018) and/or prototype robot behaviours (Azenkot et al.,
30 2016). Šabanović identified such methods as appropriate for the pursuit of a mutual shaping approach in
31 robot design, that is one which recognises the dynamic interactions between social robots and their context
32 of use (Šabanović, 2010), an approach that we find compelling for designing effective and acceptable social
33 robots efficiently. However, the automation of social robot behaviour, which requires a significant technical
34 understanding of robotics and artificial intelligence, is not typically considered during such activities.

35 Instead, common methods for the automation of social robot behaviour include utilising models based on
36 human psychology (e.g. Theory of Mind (Lemaignan et al., 2017)) or animal behaviour (Arkin et al., 2001),
37 or attempting to observe and replicate human-human interaction behaviours (e.g. (Sussenbach et al., 2014)).
38 This limits the potential for direct input from domain experts (teachers, therapists etc.) who are skilled in
39 the use of social interaction in complex scenarios. Previous work with such experts has demonstrated that a
40 lot of the related expertise is intuitive and intangible, making it difficult to access in a way that can easily
41 inform robot automation (Winkle et al., 2018). This is somewhat addressed by methods that capture domain
42 expert operation of a robot directly, for example end-user programming tools (e.g. Leonardi et al. (2019))
43 or learning from expert teleoperation of robots (e.g. Sequeira et al. (2016)). However, these methods tend to
44 focus on offline learning/programming. As such, there is no opportunity for experts to create an adequate,
45 situated mental model of the robot's capabilities, limiting the guarantee of appropriate behaviour when the
46 robot is eventually deployed to interact with users autonomously.

47 Instead, we argue that robots should be automated by domain experts themselves, in real-time, and
48 while being situated in the interaction context; and that this automation should be done through a direct,
49 bi-directional interaction between the expert and the robot. We refer to this as the *teaching phase*, where
50 the robot is taught what to do by the domain expert, regardless of whether it is, e.g. a machine learning
51 algorithm or an authoring tool that underpins this interaction. This live, in-situ and interactive approach
52 allows *mutual shaping* to occur during robot automation, as the expert defines the robot's program in
53 response to the evolving dynamics of the social context into which the robot has been deployed.

54 1.1 Supporting A Mutual Shaping Approach to Robot Design

55 Šabanović proposed a *mutual shaping* approach to social robot design, that is one which recognises
56 the dynamic interactions between social robots and their context of use, in response to their finding that
57 most roboticists were taking a technologically deterministic view of the interaction between robots and
58 society (Šabanović, 2010). Studies of real-world HRI motivate such an approach, as they demonstrate
59 how mutual shaping effects impact robot effectiveness upon deployment in the real world. For example,
60 use and acceptance of robots in older adult health settings has been shown to be affected by situational
61 and context of use factors such as user age and gender, household type, and the prompting of its use by
62 others (de Graaf et al., 2015; Chang and Šabanović, 2015) i.e. factors unrelated to the robot's functionality.
63 Pursuit of a mutual shaping approach, primarily through use of participatory design and in-the-wild robot
64 evaluation methods, gives the best possible chance of identifying and accounting for such factors during
65 the design and development process, such that the robot has maximum positive impact on its eventual
66 long-term deployment.

67 To this end, Šabanović describes four key practices that underpin a mutual shaping approach to support
68 a “*socially robust understanding of technological development that enables the participation of multiple*
69 *stakeholders and disciplines*”:

- 70 1. Evaluating robots in society: human-robot interaction studies and robot evaluations should be conducted
71 ‘in the wild’, i.e. in the environments and context of use for which they are ultimately intended to be
72 deployed (Ros et al., 2011).
- 73 2. Studying socio-technological ecologies: robot design should be informed by systematic study of the
74 context of use, and evaluation of robots should consider impact on the socio-technology ecology into
75 which they have been deployed.
- 76 3. Outside-in design: design constraints should be defined by empirical social research and the social
77 context of use, rather than technical capabilities, and evaluation should be based on user experiences
78 rather than internal measures of technical capability.
- 79 4. Designing with users: stakeholders (those who will be directly affected by the robot’s deployment and
80 use) should be included in identifying robot applications and thinking about how robots will be used as
81 well as in designing the robot and its behaviour(s).

82 However, as we explain in Section 2, robot development at present typically represents a discontinuous
83 process, particularly broken up by the automation of social robot behaviour. It still tends to heavily rely on
84 technical expertise, executed in research/development environments rather than the real-world, with little
85 active inclusion of domain experts or other expert stakeholders. This discontinuity also represents a key
86 hurdle to truly multi-disciplinary working, a disconnect between those of different academic backgrounds
87 on the research team which can result in a number of practical challenges and frustrations.

88 **1.2 The *Led-by-Experts Automation and Design Of Robots* (LEADOR) Method**

89 The generalisable method we provide in this work derives from two (independently undertaken)
90 foundational works. Firstly is Senft et al. (2019)’s educational robot for school children, in which a
91 psychologist taught a robot to support children in an educational activity. After the teaching phase with 25
92 children, the robot was evaluated in further autonomous interaction with children which demonstrated the
93 opportunity of online teaching as a way to define autonomous robot behaviours.

94 Secondly is Winkle et al. (2020)’s robot fitness coach. This work built on Senft et al. (2019) by integrating
95 the online teaching method into an end-to-end participatory design process whereby the same professional
96 fitness instructor was involved in the co-design, automation and evaluation of a robot fitness coach. This
97 work also demonstrated the value of online teaching when compared to expert-designed heuristics as a
98 next-best alternative for defining autonomous robot behaviours with domain expert involvement. Both
99 studies used a teaching phase where a domain expert interacted with the robot to create an interactive
100 behaviour, and in both studies, the resulting autonomous robot behaviour was evaluated with success.

101 From these works, we have derived a five step, generalisable method for end-to-end participatory design
102 (PD) of autonomous social robots (*Led-by-Experts Automation and Design Of Robots* or LEADOR),
103 depicted alongside typical PD in Figure 1. The key stages of our approach, as referenced in the figure, can
104 be summarised as follows:

- 105 (i) Problem Definition: *Initial brainstorming, studies of context of use, studies with stakeholders.*
- 106 (ii) Interaction Design: *Detailed refinement of robot application and interaction scenario, choice/design of*
107 *robot platform.*
- 108 (iii) System Specification: *Co-design of the robot’s action space, input space, and teaching interface.*

Figure 1. Comparison between a classic Participatory Design (PD) approach and LEADOR, our proposed end-to-end participatory design approach. Green activities represent joint work between domain experts, multidisciplinary researchers and/or engineers; yellow activities are domain expert-led; blue activities are engineer-led. Compared to typical PD, the two key differences in our approach are the focus on developing a *teaching system* instead of a *final autonomous behaviour* in step 4, and the combining of autonomous action policy definition and deployment in the real world into a single step 5 + 6. In addition, our method reduces the amount of work that is carried out independently by engineers (i.e. with no domain expert or non-roboticist input).

109 (iv) Technical Implementation: *Realisation of (iii) through technical implementation of underlying*
 110 *architecture and all sub-components and tools required for the teaching phase.*

111 (v) Real World Deployment: *Robot is deployed in the real-world, where a teaching phase is undertaken,*
 112 *led by the domain expert(s), to create autonomous robot behaviour.*

Figure 2. Three-way interaction between the domain-expert, the robot, and the target user through which the expert teaches the robot during a teaching phase upon real world deployment. Robot automation is therefore happening in the real world, while the robot is fully embedded in its long-term application context. The expert is teaching the robot through bi-directional communication, as the robot interacts with the target user. The extent of interaction(s) between the domain expert and target user should be consistent with what is envisaged for long term deployment of the robot, and is domain-dependent.

113 The cornerstone of our method is to facilitate robot automation through direct interaction between the
 114 expert and the robot, during a ‘teaching phase’ whereby the domain expert teaches the robot what to do
 115 during real interaction(s) with the target user. The resultant interaction is depicted in Figure 2. Regardless
 116 of the specifics of the final interaction, the output of this phase is a robot that *can* operate autonomously,
 117 but could also allow for continued expert-in-the-loop supervision and/or behaviour correction/additional
 118 training.

119 Through our foundational works, we demonstrate the flexibility in our method for developing autonomous
 120 robots for different long-term interaction settings. Senft et al. (2019)’s educational robot was intended
 121 for diadic, unsupervised robot-user interactions, whereas Winkle et al. (2020)’s robot fitness coach was
 122 intended primarily for diadic robot-user interactions but to be complimented with additional expert-user
 123 interactions/supervision and with additional expert-robot-user teaching interactions if necessary. LEADOR
 124 could also be used to design robots with other interaction requirements, e.g. an autonomous robot to be used
 125 in fully triadic expert-robot-user interactions or to facilitate permanent expert supervision and validation of
 126 autonomous behaviour.

127 In this paper, we have combined our experiences from these foundational works to propose an end-to-
 128 end participatory design process, centered around an in-situ teaching phase, that uniquely delivers on
 129 the promises of mutual shaping and participatory design. We suggest this approach is as *practical* as it
 130 is *responsible*, as our foundational studies demonstrate we were able to create appropriate, intelligent,
 131 autonomous social robot behaviour for complex application environments in a timely manner. As detailed
 132 in Senft et al. (2015, 2019) this teaching phase is achieved by deploying the robot in the proposed use
 133 case and it being initially controlled completely by a human ‘teacher’. The teacher can progressively
 134 improve the robot behaviour in-situ and generate a mental model of the robot’s policy. This teaching can
 135 continue until the domain expert is confident that the robot can satisfactorily operate autonomously. This

136 approach therefore allows non-roboticist, domain experts to actively participate in creating autonomous
137 robot behaviour. It also allows for the continual shaping of robot behaviour, as teaching can be seamlessly
138 (re-)continued at any time to address any changes in the interaction dynamics, therefore better supporting a
139 mutual shaping approach. We suggest our methodology is particularly appropriate for use cases in which
140 difficult-to-automate and/or difficult-to-explain ‘intuitive’ human domain expertise and experience are
141 needed to inform personalised interaction and engagement (e.g. socially assistive robotics). The result
142 then, is an autonomous robot which has been designed, developed and evaluated (by a multi-disciplinary
143 research team) directly in conjunction with domain experts, within its real-world context of use, that can
144 intelligently respond to complex social dynamics in ways that would have otherwise been very difficult to
145 automate.

146 For clarity, hereafter we use the term *domain expert* (or *teacher*) to refer to experts in an application
147 domain. For example, these domain experts could be therapists, shop owners, or school teachers. These
148 experts interact with the robot and specify its behaviour in a *teaching interaction* (even if no actual machine
149 learning might be involved). On the other hand, *engineers* or developers refer to people with technical
150 expertise in robotics or programming. They are the ones typically programming a robot behaviour or
151 developing tools to be used by domain experts. Finally, the *target user* is the person a robot would interact
152 with in the *application interaction*. For example, such target users could be children during a therapy
153 session or store customers in a shopping interaction. This population is expected to interact with the robot
154 at the point of use, rather than be the ones directly defining the autonomous robot behaviour.

2 RELATED WORK

155 2.1 Participatory Design

156 Participatory design (PD) is fundamentally concerned with involving the people who will use and/or
157 will be affected by a technology in the design of that technology, with a focus on mutual learning
158 between participants who typically represent either *domain experts* (users) or *technology experts*
159 (designers) (Simonsen and Robertson, 2012). Contemporary PD has been concerned with combining
160 typical, iterative PD practices with evaluation of the design in use under the concept of *sustained PD* or
161 design as ‘emerging change’ (Simonsen et al., 2010, 2014). Originally posed in the context of large-scale
162 information-systems projects, the Sustained PD approach presented by Simonsen and Hertzum (2012)’s
163 emphasises the evaluation of systems by exposing them to real—situated work practices, but also notes
164 associated challenges regarding management of a stepwise implementation process and the conducting of
165 realistic, large-scale PD experiments.

166 This focus on implementation of the new technology as part of PD also therefore raises the notion of
167 user participation in that implementation process. Fléron et al. (2012) demonstrated this in the context of
168 first designing an electronic whiteboard with healthcare practitioners, followed by healthcare practitioner-
169 led implementation of that whiteboard at two emergency departments. Notably this work investigated
170 differences in the experiences between staff who did and did not participate in this implementation process.
171 Specifically, the participating staff (those responsible for the system implementation) identified some
172 difficulties in understanding their role/responsibilities. The non-participating staff expressed a desire for
173 earlier (pre-deployment) testing of the system, but demonstrated positive ‘buy-in’ of the system nonetheless,
174 with the authors positing this linked to reputed credibility of the system given it was (co-)developed and
175 implemented by their peers. This points towards the potential benefits. but also the challenges when trying
176 to include end users and/or domain experts in this sustained PD process.

177 Specifically concerning PD, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, Bratteteig and Verne (2018)
178 note three key challenges when using PD with/for AI systems. Firstly, users and designers might struggle
179 to conceptualise the possibilities and limitation of AI, secondly that (machine learning-based) AI systems
180 develop over time and hence are difficult to evaluate within a typical PD experimental period and finally
181 how to distinguish between ‘normal’ use and training. Overall, the authors conclude AI and machine
182 learning can be part of a PD process, but that AI poses complex challenges that go beyond the scope of
183 typical PD projects.

184 From the PD literature then, there is a clear motivation to explore PD processes which go beyond
185 initial design to also include implementation, and to understand how best to approach the PD of machine
186 learning based AI systems. The notion of using expert-in-the-loop machine learning for sustained PD
187 that also includes implementation specifically sits at this exact intersection. However, whilst many
188 contemporary PD works have described applications in the development and implementation of information
189 technology systems, there seem to be very few (if any) which consider autonomous, social robot design
190 and development. Considering literature from the human-robot-interaction (HRI) field however, a number
191 of (interdisciplinary) HRI researchers have utilised and drawn from PD in the context of designing robots
192 and their applications.

193 2.1.1 Participatory Design in Social Robotics

194 Here we identify relevant works utilising PD and other related methodologies specifically in the context
195 of designing social human-robot interaction. Notably these works primarily originate from the HRI
196 community, as opposed to the PD community, but most such works showcase one (or more) of the
197 following methodologies:

- 198 1. *Ethnographic/‘In-the-Wild’ Studies*: typically focusing on understanding situated use and/or emergent
199 behaviour(s) on deployment of a robot into the real world. Concerning robot design, such studies are
200 inherently limited to the testing of prototypes, WoZ systems or finished products (e.g. Forlizzi (2007);
201 Chang and Šabanović (2015)). However, they might be used to inform initial design requirements (and
202 their iteration) through observation of the use case environment and user behaviour.
- 203 2. *User-Centered Design (UCD)*: aiming to understand and incorporate user perspective and needs into
204 robot design. Typically researchers set the research agenda based on prior assumptions regarding the
205 context of use and proposed robot application (e.g. Louie et al. (2014); Wu et al. (2012); Beer et al.
206 (2012)).
- 207 3. *Participatory Design (PD)*: encouraging participants (users, stakeholders etc.) to actively join in
208 decision making processes which shape robot design and/or the direction of research. This typically
209 involves participants having equal authority as the researchers and designers, with both engaging in a
210 two-way exchange of knowledge and ideas (e.g. Azenkot et al. (2016); Björling and Rose (2019)).

211 Lee et al. give a good overview of the above practices as employed in social robot and HRI design/research,
212 with a particular focus on how the shortcomings of 1 and 2 can be addressed using PD (Lee et al., 2017).
213 The authors use a case study of social robot PD from their own work to highlight a number of PD
214 design principles for informing social robot design and further development of PD methodologies. They
215 particularly highlight the empowering of PD participants to become active ‘robot co-designers’ through
216 *mutual learning*, as introduced previously, whereby there is a two way exchange of knowledge and
217 experience between researchers/designers and expert stakeholders. Through this process, users learn
218 about e.g. robot capabilities, such that they are better informed to contribute to discussions on potential

219 applications, whilst the researchers/designers come to learn more about the realities of the proposed context
220 of use from the users' perspective.

221 Since publication of Lee et al.'s work, PD methods have been gaining visibility for the design of social
222 robots, with other roboticists further refining PD methods and best practice for their use in social robotics
223 and HRI. As such, PD works relating to ours can be grouped into two categories:

224 (i) results-focused publications which utilised PD methods.

225 (ii) methodology-focused publications in which the authors share or reflect on PD methods for use in
226 social robot/HRI design.

227 Works on (i) have typically taken the form of researchers working closely with prospective users
228 and/or other stakeholders via focus groups, interviews, workshops etc. with the researchers then
229 concatenating their results to produce potential use case scenarios (Jenkins and Draper, 2015), design
230 guidelines/recommendations (Winkle et al., 2018) and/or prototype robot behaviours (Azenkot et al., 2016).
231 For example, Azenkot et al. (2016) used participatory design to generate specifications for a socially
232 assistive robot for guiding blind people through a building. The authors' study consisted of multiple
233 sessions including interviews, a group workshop and individual user-robot prototyping sessions. The initial
234 interviews were used, in part, to brief participants about robot capabilities. The group session was used to
235 develop a conceptual storyboard of robot use, identifying interactions between the robot guide and the user.

236 Winkle et al. (2018) conducted a study with therapists, utilising a novel focus group methodology
237 combined with follow-up individual interviews in order to generate an expert-informed set of design
238 guidelines for informing the design and use of socially assistive robots in rehabilitative therapies. The
239 topic guides for each part of the study were designed to help the researchers understand typical therapy
240 practice and therapist best practices for improving patient engagement and to explore therapists' ideas and
241 opinions on the potential role(s) social robots might play in rehabilitation. A key finding of this work was
242 the extent to which therapists' intuitive, instantaneous behaviour is driven by situational factors specific
243 to each individual client, making it difficult, for example, to extract any clear cut heuristics that might
244 inform generalisable, autonomous social robot behaviour directly. The resultant design guidelines therefore
245 suggested that socially assistive robots require 'high-level' personalisation to each user as well as the ability
246 to adapt, in real time, to e.g. the user's performance and other situational factors. This is one of the key
247 works that motivates our effort to therefore facilitate expert-led, in-situ robot teaching, in order to capture
248 this sort of tacit social intelligence.

249 A follow up publication by the same authors then comes under category (ii). Specifically, the authors
250 provide more detail on their focus group methodology, and how it reflects a mutual shaping approach
251 to social robot design, alongside a general guide in how it might be applied to other domains (Winkle
252 et al., 2019a). The method combines elements of PD and UCD, and utilises a demonstration of robot
253 capabilities to support mutual learning between the researchers and participants. To evidence how this
254 method supported mutual shaping in their work, and why this was beneficial, the authors identify specific
255 project-related considerations as well as new research directions that could only be identified in conjunction
256 with their domain expert participants, and also note that taking part in a focus group significantly (positively)
257 impacted on participants' acceptance of social robots.

258 Further on (ii), Björling and Rose (2019) shared PD methods they used in the context of taking an
259 overall *human-centered design* approach to co-designing robots for improved mental health with teens.
260 They present three method cases which cover novel and creative participatory techniques such as research

261 design, script-writing and prototyping, concluding with a set of participatory design principles for guiding
262 design work with vulnerable participants in a human-centred domain. One of their methods revolved
263 around inviting teens to act as WoZ robot operators. Specifically, their setup had one teen teleoperating
264 a robot whilst another teen recounted a (pre-scripted) stressful experience. In a second experiment, they
265 utilised virtual reality (VR) such that one teen interacted, in an immersive VR environment, with a robot
266 avatar teleoperated by a teen outside of that VR environment. From this study, the authors gathered data
267 about the way teens collaborate and their perceptions of robot roles and behaviours. To this end, they
268 demonstrated the value in expert (user) teleoperation of a proposed robot, both for better understanding the
269 use case requirements and user needs, but also as a way to generate exemplars of desirable autonomous
270 robot behaviour. Alves-Oliveira et al. (2017) also demonstrated a similar use of puppeteering and roleplay
271 methods as part of a co-design study with children.

272 In summary, work to date has demonstrated how PD methods can be used to study a proposed application
273 domain in an attempt to ensure researchers thoroughly understand the context of use, and to elicit some
274 expert knowledge for informing robot design and automation. This goes some way to supporting a mutual
275 shaping and responsible robotics approach to social robot development. However, there remains two key
276 disconnects in delivering truly end-to-end PD and mutual shaping in development of an autonomous social
277 robot. Firstly, robot automation is informed but not controlled or developed by domain experts. Secondly,
278 there is a disconnect between this program definition and the real-world interaction requirements and
279 situational specificities that will likely be crucial to overall robot success when deployed in real world
280 interaction.

281 **2.2 Alternative Methods to Capture Domain-Expert Knowledge**

282 One of the key assumptions of PD in the context of robotics research is that the knowledge of the
283 desired robot behaviour is held by domain experts and needs to be translated into programs. Typically,
284 this translation is made by engineers, obtaining a number of heuristics from the domain experts and
285 consequently automating the robot. Although widely applied even in PD research, this method only
286 partially delivers on the promises of PD, as domain experts are used to inform robot behaviours but still
287 rely on external actors (the engineers) to transform their intuition, knowledge, and expertise into actual
288 code. Furthermore, this process can lead to a number of communication issues as members from different
289 communities have different ways of expressing needs and desires. Nevertheless, there exists a number
290 of alternative solutions to capture domain-expert knowledge that could support a PD approach to robot
291 automation.

292 **2.2.1 End-user programming tools**

293 A first solution is to create tools to allow domain-experts to create robot behaviours themselves. Research
294 in end-user development, or end-user programming, explores tools to allow domain experts or end-users to
295 create programs without requiring coding knowledge. Typical applications are home automation, application
296 synchronisation (e.g., IFTTT or Microsoft Flow), or video games development. Additionally, end-user
297 programming has seen large interest in robotics, for example to create autonomous robot behaviours for
298 both industrial robots (Paxton et al., 2017; Gao and Huang, 2019) and social robots (Leonardi et al., 2019;
299 Louie and Nejat, 2020). These *authoring* tools are often developed by engineers and then provided to users
300 to create their own applications without relying on text-based coding, for example by using visual or block
301 programming (Huang and Cakmak, 2017), tangible interfaces (Porfirio et al., 2021), or augmented reality
302 (Cao et al., 2019).

303 However, while being more friendly for users, such methods still suffer from two main drawbacks. First,
304 the interface is often developed by engineers without necessarily following principles of participatory

305 design. Second, these methods often see the programming process as a discrete step leading to a static
306 autonomous behaviour with limited opportunity to update the robot behaviour or little focus on testing
307 and evaluating the created behaviour in real interactions. More precisely, users of these tools might not
308 be the actual target of the application interaction and would program robots outside of the real context
309 of use, forcing the aspiring developers to rely on their internal simulation of how the interaction should
310 happen. For example, a shop owner could use an authoring tool to create a welcoming behaviour for a
311 social robot, test it on themselves while developing the behaviour and then deploying it on real clients with
312 limited safeguards. In such process, developer have to use their best guess to figure out how people might
313 interact with the robot, and often have issues to infuse the robot with tacit knowledge, such as timing for
314 actions or proxemics. This disconnect can lead to suboptimal robot behaviour as the robot will face edge
315 cases in the real world that the designer might not have anticipated.

316 2.2.2 Learning from Real-World Interaction(s)

317 A method to address this gap between an offline design phase and the real world is to mimic the expert
318 while they perform the interaction. Using machine learning, systems can learn from the experts how robots
319 should behave. For example, Liu et al. (2016) asked participants to role play an interaction between a
320 shopkeeper and a client and recorded data about this interaction (e.g., participants location or speech). From
321 these recordings, Liu et al. learned a model of the shopkeeper, transferred it to the robot, and evaluated
322 it human-robot interactions. Similarly, Porfirio et al. (2019) recorded interaction traces between human
323 actors and formalized them into finite state machine to create a robot behaviour. While relying on simulated
324 interactions, these methods provide more opportunities to developers to explore situations outside of their
325 initial imagination.

326 One assumption of these methods is that robots should replicate human behaviour. Consequently,
327 such methods allow the capture of implicit behaviours such as the timing and idiosyncrasies of human
328 interactions. However, real-world interactions with robots might follow social norms different from
329 ones between humans only. Consequently, learning directly from human-human interaction also presents
330 limitations.

331 Wizard of Oz (WoZ) is an interaction paradigm widely used in robotics (Riek, 2012) whereby a robot is
332 controlled by an expert deciding what actions the robot should execute and when. The main advantage of
333 this paradigm is to ensure that the robot behaviour is at all times appropriate to the current interaction. For
334 this reason, WoZ has been extensively used in Robot-Assisted Therapy and exploratory studies to explore
335 how humans react to robots. Recent research has explored how this interaction can be used to collect data
336 from real human-robot interaction and learn an appropriate robot behaviour. Knox et al. (2014) proposed
337 the “Learning from the Wizard” paradigm, whereby a robot would first be controlled in a WoZ experiment
338 used to acquire the demonstrations and then machine learning would be applied offline to define a policy.
339 Sequeira et al. (2016) extended and applied this Learning from Demonstration (LfD), with an emphasis on
340 the concept of “Restricted-perception WoZ”, in which the wizard only has access to the same input space
341 as the learning algorithm, thus reducing the problem of correspondence between the state and action spaces
342 used by the wizard and the ones available to the robot controller. Both of these works could support a PD
343 approach to robot automation, as they could be used to generate an autonomous robot action policy based
344 on data from (non-roboticist) domain expert WoZ interactions in real-world environments.

345 Nevertheless, the typical WoZ puppeteering setup results in an absence of interaction between the
346 design/development team and the robot, which prevents designers from having a realistic mental model
347 of the robot behaviour and does not allow for any mutual shaping between the wizard, the robot and
348 the contextual environment. Traditionally, LfD separates data collecting and learning into distinct steps,

349 limiting the opportunity to know during the teleoperated data collection process at what point ‘enough’
350 training data has actually been collected, as the system can only be evaluated once the learning process is
351 complete. Similarly, when using end-user programming methods there is little opportunity to know how the
352 system would actually behave when deployed in the real world. This lack of knowledge about the actual
353 robot behaviour implies that robots have to be deployed to interact in the real world with limited guarantees
354 or safeguards ensuring their behaviours are actually efficient in the desired interaction.

355 2.2.3 Interactive Machine Learning

356 Interactive Machine Learning (IML) refers to a system learning online while it is being used (Fails and
357 Olsen Jr, 2003; Amershi et al., 2014). The premise of IML is to empower end-users while reducing the
358 iteration time between subsequent improvement of a learning system. Using IML to create robot behaviours
359 through an interaction between a designer and a autonomous agent allows for full utilisation of the expert’s
360 teaching skills. It has been shown that humans are skilled teachers who can react to a learner’s current
361 performance and provide information specifically relevant to them (Bloom, 1984). Similarly, previous
362 research showed that this effect also exists, to a certain extent, when teaching robots. Using Socially
363 Guided Machine Learning (Thomaz and Breazeal, 2008) a human teacher adapts their teaching strategy to
364 robot behaviour and thus helps it to learn better. If able to observe (and correct) the robot’s autonomous
365 behaviour, seeing the result of the robot behaviour as it progresses, the expert can create a model of
366 the robot’s knowledge, capabilities and limitations. This understanding of the robot reduces the risk of
367 over-trusting (both during training and/or autonomous operation) and introduces the potential for expert
368 evaluation to become part of the verification and validation process.

3 A BLUEPRINT FOR END-TO-END PARTICIPATORY DESIGN

369 We identify the following requirements to extend participatory design into an *end-to-end* methodology, that
370 include the co-design of the robot’s automated behaviour. Such a method needs to allow for:

- 371 1. Systematic observation and study of the use case environment in which the robot is to ultimately be
372 deployed;
- 373 2. Inclusion and empowerment of relevant stakeholders (users, domain experts) from the initial design
374 phases, such that design and application of the robot/interaction scenario is co-produced by researchers
375 and stakeholders together;
- 376 3. (Safe and responsible) evaluation of prototypes in the real-world environment(s) into which the robot
377 is eventually intended to be deployed;
- 378 4. Inclusion of relevant stakeholders in creation of autonomous robot behaviours, which should utilise
379 interaction data collected in the real-world;
- 380 5. Two-way interaction between the domain-expert ‘teacher’ (e.g., a therapist) or designer and robot
381 ‘learner’ such that the teacher can better understand the state of the robot/to what extent learning
382 ‘progress’ is being made and hence adapt their teaching appropriately/flag any significant design issues;
- 383 6. Inclusion of relevant stakeholders (e.g., parents of a child in therapy) in (safe) evaluation of autonomous
384 robot behaviours, as they perform in the real-world.

385 Requirements 1 and 2 can be addressed by the typical PD methods discussed in Section 2.1.1, and
386 requirements 3 and 6 can be addressed by carefully designed ‘in-the-wild’ studies. In our work, we
387 therefore look to specifically tackle requirements 4 and 5 by demonstrating how robot automation can be
388 approached as an in-situ, triadic interaction between domain expert teacher(s), robot learner and target end

Table 1. Key outcomes of and appropriate tools for each stage of LEADOR.

	Outcomes	Tools
1. Problem Definition	Domain understanding	Ethnographic studies, focus groups, brainstorming
2. Interaction Design	Interaction scenario, robot selection/design	Workshop, role-playing, low-tech prototyping
3. System Specification	State-Action space for the robot, teaching tools	Brainstorming, behaviour prototyping
4. Technical Implementation	Robot system (sensors and actions), teaching system (authoring tools or learning algorithm)	Software development, lab studies, testing workshops
5. Real-World Deployment	Delivering on the application target, autonomous robot	In-situ teaching by expert

389 user(s). With LEADOR, we showcase how this approach can be integrated into one continuous, end-to-end
 390 PD process that satisfies all of the above requirements.

391 Table 1 summarises the key outcomes of, and some potential tools for each stage of LEADOR. Figure 1
 392 shows how these steps compare to typical PD, as well as who (domain experts and/or engineers) are
 393 involved at each stage. Each stage is detailed in full below. Table 2 shows how these steps have been
 394 derived from/were represented in our two foundational studies.

395 **3.1 Step 1: Problem Definition**

396 As noted in Figure 1, Step 1 of our method aligns to best practice use of PD as previously demonstrated
 397 in social robotics. The purpose of this stage is to generate a thorough understanding of the use context in
 398 which the robot is to be deployed, and to invite stakeholders to influence and shape the proposed application.
 399 It would likely include observations, focus groups and/or interviews with a variety of stakeholders.

400 The focus group methodology presented in (Winkle et al., 2019a) is one appropriate method that could
 401 be used for engaging with stakeholders at this stage as it facilitates expert establishment of non-roboticists,
 402 broad discussion of the application context (without presentation of a pre-defined research agenda),
 403 participant reflection on the context of use ‘as is’ and researcher-led sharing of technical expertise; followed
 404 by detailed consideration and refinement of the research agenda based on researchers and participants now
 405 being equal co-designers.

406 **3.2 Step 2: Interaction Design**

407 Similarly to Step 1, Step 2 of our method also aligns to best practice use of PD as previously demonstrated
 408 in social robotics. The purpose of this stage is to define and refine the interaction scenario(s) the proposed
 409 robot will engage in, and hence the functionalities/capabilities it might require. The robot platform should
 410 also be chosen at this stage. For simplicity here we have equated robot platform *choice* with robot platform
 411 *design*. Much current social robotics research utilises off-the-shelf robot platforms (e.g. Pepper and NAO
 412 from Softbank Robotics) but others focus on the design of new and/or application-specific platforms. Either
 413 can be appropriate for LEADOR as long as the choice/design is participatory with stakeholders (for a good
 414 example of PD in design of a novel robot, see Alves-Oliveira et al. 2017’s work on designing the YOLO
 415 robot.

416 Focusing then on more specific application of the robot and the interaction(s) it should engage in,
417 methods for PD might include focus groups and similar as per Step 1, but could also include more novel
418 and/or creative PD activities such as script writing (Björling and Rose, 2019), roleplaying (including also
419 stakeholder teleoperation of the robot) (Björling and Rose, 2019; Alves-Oliveira et al., 2017) and accessible,
420 ‘low-tech’ prototyping (Valencia et al., 2021).

421 Note that there is an important interaction design decision to be made here regarding what final deployment
422 of the robot ‘looks like’ in terms of long term oversight by/presence of domain expert(s) (those involved
423 in it’s co-design or otherwise) and the role those experts play with regards to the target user. This can be
424 reflected in the teaching interaction setup, specifically with regards to the amount of interaction between
425 the domain expert(s) and target users (see Figure 2). For example, it was decided early on in the design
426 of Winkle et al. (2020)’s fitness coach robot that there was no intention to ever fully remove the expert
427 presence from the interaction environment. As an alternative, in Senft et al. (2019) the intention from the
428 onset was to create a fully autonomous and independent robot that interacted alone with the target users.
429 Such decisions regarding the role of domain experts would ultimately emerge (explicitly or implicitly) in
430 conjunction with deciding the robot’s functionalities and the further system specification undertaken in
431 Step 3. However, this long-term desired role of the domain expert(s) should be made clear, explicitly, at
432 this stage, such that it can be reflected in the approach to program definition.

433 **3.3 Step 3: System Specification**

434 As shown in Figure 1, it is at this stage that our method begins to diverge from the typical PD process,
435 although we continue to utilise PD methods. This step is concerned with co-design of system specificities
436 required to (i) deliver the interaction design resulting from Step 2 and (ii) facilitate expert-led teaching
437 phase on real-world deployment that is fundamental to our method (see Step 5). In summary, the aim
438 of this step is to co-design the robot’s action space, input space, and the tool(s) required to facilitate the
439 bi-directional teaching interaction between the domain expert and the robot. There is also some similarity
440 here to the design process for a WoZ or teleoperated system, which would also require design of the robot’s
441 action space and an interface for (non-roboticist) teleoperation of the robot. The key difference here is the
442 additional requirement to specify the robot’s input space and the choice of teaching tools for the move
443 towards autonomy during Step 5.

444 **3.4 Step 4: Technical Implementation**

445 The main development effort for our method lies in producing the full architecture and tools to allow
446 domain experts to specify autonomous robot behaviour. We note here that the technical implementation
447 required is likely to be greater than that required for a typical WoZ setup and might not be simpler than
448 heuristics-based robot controller.

449 Four main components need to be developed during this phase:

- 450 1. Set of high-level actions for the robot.
- 451 2. Set of sensory inputs that will be used to drive the future robot behaviour.
- 452 3. A representation of the program which will encode autonomous behaviour.
- 453 4. Expert tools to specify the mapping between the sensory state and the actions.

454 With our method, the program representation could take the shape of a machine learning algorithm
455 taking inputs from the expert via the interface and learning a mapping between the current state of the
456 world when the action was selected and the action itself (the approach taken in our foundational works).
457 Alternatively, the representation could allow the expert to encode a program explicitly, for example through

458 state machines, or trigger-action programming, while allowing the expert to update the program in real
459 time, and control the robot actions to ensure that they are constantly appropriate.

460 A typical automation system would replace the expert tools with an actual definition of the behaviour
461 making use of the program representation to map sensors to actions and define fully an autonomous
462 behaviour. On the other end of the spectrum, a WoZ setup might not need a representation of the program,
463 but instead would rely on the interface to display relevant sensory inputs to the wizard (if any) and allow
464 them to select what action to do.

465 **3.5 Step 5: Real World Deployment and Teaching Phase**

466 Undertaking robot automation (and evaluation) in-the-wild is a key part of LEADOR. To satisfy
467 requirements 5 and 6 as laid out in the introduction, support a mutual shaping approach to robot design,
468 and ensure appropriate robot behaviour, the *teaching phase* should adhere to the following:

- 469 1. it must be undertaken in situ, i.e., in the context of the final context of use, and with the real target
470 population.
- 471 2. it must utilise a domain expert teaching the robot as it delivers on the application interaction.
- 472 3. the expert-robot interaction should be bi-directional, i.e., the expert should be able to define and/or
473 refine the robot's autonomous behaviour policy, while the robot informs the expert about its status.

474 Requirement 1 ensures that the approach is ecologically valid, and that the information used by the expert
475 for the automation are suited to the real challenges and idiosyncrasies of the desired context of use.

476 Requirement 2 ensures that people with domain knowledge can encode that knowledge in the robot.
477 Furthermore, the presence of the expert should be used to ensure that the robot is expressing an appropriate
478 behaviour at all times. As the teaching happens in the real world, with the real users, there is limited space
479 for trial and error. The expert can be used as a safeguard to ensure appropriate robot behaviour even in the
480 initial phases of the teaching.

481 Requirement 3 ensures that the expert can create a mental model of the robot behaviour. This point
482 is a key difference to non-interactive teaching methods such as the ones based on offline learning (e.g.,
483 Sequeira et al. 2016). With the robot's feedback on its policy (through suggestions or visual behaviour
484 representation), the expert can assess the robot's (evolving) capabilities and decide what inputs would
485 improve the robot's policy further.

486 Finally, during this real-world deployment, if the robot is ultimately expected to interact
487 autonomously/unsupervised, the expert can use their mental model of the robot behaviour to decide
488 when enough teaching has been done and when the robot is ready to interact autonomously. By relying
489 on online teaching, this decision does not have to be final as the expert could seamlessly step back into
490 the teacher position when the robot interacts with sensitive populations or if the robot requires additional
491 refinement of its policy.

492 **4 FOUNDATIONAL STUDIES**

492 The LEADOR method is primarily derived from two foundational studies made by the authors, which
493 were themselves informed by the authors' previous experiences working with domain experts in the design
494 of social robots. The first one, presented in Senft et al. (2019), explores a study with 75 children how
495 the teaching interaction could be used to create an autonomous robot behaviour. As shown in Table 2,
496 this study did not employ PD, the authors, researchers in HRI, did the early steps by themselves based
497 on their previous related experiences. The second one, presented in Winkle et al. (2020), built on the

	School Based Educational Robot	Gym Based Robot Fitness Coach
Step 1	Decision by researchers based on experience to focus on learning food chain around an educational game for children of age 8-10.	Researchers identified the NHS C25K exercise programme based on research goals (longitudinal, real-world HRI) but worked with a fitness instructor to observe typical environment and refine problem definition.
Step 2	Decision by researchers to focus on robot-user interaction, with expert only providing robot commands and oversight of the robot behavior to ensure that each action is validated by them. Goal is to evaluate the creation of an autonomous robot.	Decision in conjunction with the fitness instructor that the robot would lead exercise sessions (in which he would minimise interaction with exercisers) but that he would provide additional support (e.g. health advice, stretching) outside of these. Goal is to create and demonstrate an effective, real-world SAR based intervention via PD (as responsible robotics).
Step 3	Using SPARC Senft et al. (2015) as interaction framework, robot state and action spaces defined by researchers. Teaching through a GUI on a tablet.	Also using SPARC Senft et al. (2015) the robot state and action spaces as well as the teaching GUI were all co-designed with the fitness instructor.
Step 4	Implementation of all the actions and learning algorithm. Prototype evaluation in lab. Initial pilot study in schools for evaluating the game with the target population and used as teacher training.	Implementation of all the actions and learning algorithm. Fitness instructor provided all dialogue for robot actions. Prototype evaluation was undertaken in the lab and in the final study gym environment, final robot placement and system installation details were also decided in conjunction with the fitness instructor.
Step 5	Deployment in two local schools with more than 100 children over multiple months. Between-subject evaluation with three conditions: a passive robot, a supervised robot (during the teaching interaction), and an autonomous unsupervised robot.	Deployed in to the university gym for teaching and autonomous evaluation through delivery of the C25K programme (27 sessions over 9-12 weeks) to 10 participants. Ran a total of 232 exercise sessions of which 151 were used for teaching the IML system, 32 were used for evaluating the IML system when allowed to run autonomously and 49 were used to test a heuristic-based 'control' condition (all testing was within-subject).

Table 2. Overview of activities undertaken in the two case studies as exemplars for applying our generalised methodology. See Table 4 for a pictorial 'storyboard' of this process and the co-design activities undertaken for development of the Robot Fitness Coach.

498 first study by utilising the same teaching approach to robot automation, but incorporating that into and
 499 end-to-end participatory design process to support mutual shaping. The end goal of each study was also
 500 slightly different, as Senft et al. (2019) aimed to produce a robot that would ultimately interact with users
 501 with little-no further expert involvement. Winkle et al. (2020) also aimed to produce an autonomous robot
 502 that would primarily interact 1:1 with users, but with no desire to remove the expert, who would have their
 503 own interactions with the users, and/or provide provide additional teaching to the robot should they deem it
 504 necessary.

505 **4.1 Study 1: Evaluating the Teaching Interaction**

506 The goal of this first study was to evaluate if the teaching interaction could be used to create autonomous
507 social behaviours Senft et al. (2019). This study was designed by the authors, who had experience designing
508 robots for the application domain, but did not involve external stakeholders such as teachers.

509 During the problem definition phase, researchers decide to contextualize the work in robot tutoring for
510 children, and explore questions such as how robots can provide appropriate comments to children (both in
511 term of context and time) to stimulate learning. This work was based on experience and knowledge from
512 the researchers about educational robotics.

513 During the interaction design phase, researchers decided to focus the application interaction around an
514 educational game where children could move animals on a screen and understand food nets. This part
515 included an initial prototype of the game. As the goal was to explore how autonomous behaviours could be
516 created, the teacher was not involved in the game activity, only the robot was interacting with the child.
517 The robot used was a NAO robot from Softbank Robotics.

518 In the system specification, the state and action spaces of the interaction were selected. Examples of state
519 include game-related component (e.g. distance between animal) and social dynamics elements (e.g. timing
520 since last action of each agents). The robot's actions were divided into five categories: encouragements,
521 congratulations, hints, drawing attention and reminding rules. The teacher-robot interaction used SPARC
522 Senft et al. (2015).

523 In the technical implementation phase, the learning algorithm was developed, tested and interfaced with
524 the other elements of the system. The teaching interface was also created in such a way as to allow the
525 teacher to select actions for the robot to execute and receive suggestions from the robot. At this stage,
526 initial prototypes were tested in lab studies and schools.

527 In the real-world deployment, authors evaluated the system in two different schools with 75 children. The
528 study adopted a between-participant design and explored three conditions: a passive robot, a supervised
529 robot (referring to the teaching interaction), and an autonomous robot (where the teacher was removed
530 from the interaction and the learning algorithm disabled).

531 Results from the study showed that the teaching interaction allowed the teacher to provide demonstrations
532 to the robot to support learning in the real world. The teacher used the teaching interaction to create a
533 mental model of the robot behaviour. When deployed to interact autonomously, the robot enacted a policy
534 presenting similarities with the one used by the teacher in the teaching phase: the frequency of actions was
535 similar and the robot captured relation and timing between specific events and actions (e.g. a congratulation
536 action should normally be executed around two seconds after an eating event from the child's actions).
537 Overall, this study demonstrated that human can teach robot social policy from in-situ guidance.

538 **4.2 Study 2: Teaching Interaction as Participatory Design**

539 The goal of this study was to use the teaching interaction approach to facilitate creation of a fully expert-
540 informed/expert-in-the-loop autonomous socially assistive robot-based intervention for the real-world. The
541 fundamental activity to be delivered by robot, the NHS C25K programme, was selected by the researchers
542 based on this research goal; but all study implementation details were decided and designed in conjunction
543 with a domain expert (fitness instructor) throughout. Given the end-to-end and constant expert involvement
544 for this study there was seamless progression and some overlap between the problem definition, interaction
545 design and system specification phases as we present them for LEADOR. A number of co-design activities
546 were undertaken (over a total of 6 sessions totalling approx. 12.5 hours) which ultimately covered all of
547 these key phases, sometimes in parallel, allowing for iteration of the overall study design.

548 Problem definition was achieved by researchers working with the fitness instructor to (i) understand how
549 a programme like C25K would be delivered by a (human) fitness instructor and (ii) explore the potential
550 role a social robot might take in supporting such an intervention. This involved the researchers visiting the
551 university gym and undertaking mock exercise sessions with the instructor, and the instructor visiting the
552 robotics lab to see demonstrations of the proposed robot platform and a presentation by the researchers on
553 their previous works and project goals. The robot used was a Pepper robot from Softbank Robotics.

554 For the interaction design, the researchers and fitness instructor agreed that exercise sessions would be led
555 by the robot and primarily represent robot-user interactions, with the fitness instructor supervising from a
556 distance and only interacting to ensure safety (e.g. in the case of over exertion). As this study also aimed to
557 test (within-subject) the appropriateness of resultant autonomous behaviours, it was decided to purposefully
558 leave the details of the fitness instructor's role somewhat ambiguous to exercising participants. The
559 instructor was not hidden away during the interaction and it was clear he was supervising the overall study,
560 but exercisers were not aware of the extent to which he was or wasn't engaging in teaching interactions
561 with the robot during sessions. As noted in Section 3, deciding on what long term deployment should
562 'look like' in terms of robot-user-expert interactions is a key design requirement at this stage. For the robot
563 fitness coach, we imagined a 'far future' scenario, where one of our robot fitness coaches would be installed
564 next to every treadmill on a gym floor, supervised by one human fitness instructor. That instructor would
565 ensure exercisers' physical safety and still play a role in their motivation and engagement as human-human
566 interaction is known to do. This type of interaction with one expert, multiple robots and multiple target
567 users is a common goal in many assistive robot applications where some tasks could be automated, but
568 there is a desire to keep an expert presence to e.g. maintain important human-human interactions and
569 ensure user safety.

570 The system specification represented somewhat of a 'negotiation' between the researchers and the fitness
571 instructor, as he identified the kind of high level action and inputs he felt the robot ought to have, and the
572 researchers identified how feasible that might be for technical implementation. The state space consisted
573 of static and dynamic features that were designed to capture exerciser engagement, task performance
574 and motivation/personality; all identified by the fitness instructor as being relevant to his decisions in
575 undertaking fitness instruction himself and hence teaching the robot how best to interact with a particular
576 participant. The action space was divided into two categories: task actions and social supporting actions.
577 The task actions were fundamentally set by the C25K programme (i.e. when to run or walk and for how
578 long at a time). The social supporting actions were then broken down into eight sub-categories covering
579 time reminders, social interaction, performance feedback, praise, checking on the user, robot animation and
580 two proxemics-related actions (leaning towards/away from the user). Importantly, system specification for
581 this study also included co-designing the GUI that would facilitate the bi-directional teaching interaction
582 (also utilising SPARC Senft et al. (2015)) between the robot and the fitness instructor with the fitness
583 instructor himself.

584 The technical implementation phase essentially mirrored that of Study 1: the learning algorithm was
585 developed, tested and interfaced with the other elements of the system. The teaching interface was also
586 finalised based on the co-design activities described previously, and similarly allowed the fitness instructor
587 to select actions for the robot and to respond to its suggestions. Initial prototypes of both the robot and the
588 GUI were tested in lab studies and the final gym environment.

589 In the real-world deployment, researchers evaluated the system in a university gym with 10 participants
590 recruited to undertake the 27-session C25K programme over a maximum of 12 weeks. The study adopted
591 a within-subject design and explored three conditions: a supervised robot (referring to the teaching

592 interaction), an autonomous robot (where the fitness instructor was still in position but allowed all learner-
593 suggested actions to auto-execute) and a heuristic-based autonomous robot; a ‘control’ condition for
594 comparing the ‘teaching interaction as PD’ approach to, representing a ‘next-best’ alternative for generating
595 expert-informed autonomous behaviour.

596 Results from the study again demonstrated the feasibility of SPARC and IML for generating autonomous
597 socially assistive robot behaviour, suggested that the expert-robot teaching interaction approach can have
598 a positive impact on robot acceptability (by the domain expert and targets users) and that the teaching
599 approach yields better autonomous behaviour than expert informed heuristics as a ‘next best’ alternative for
600 expert-informed autonomous behaviour creation.

601 **4.3 Evidence of Mutual Shaping**

602 Typical PD facilitates mutual shaping as it allows non-roboticist, domain experts to shape research goals,
603 design guidelines, and evaluate robot prototypes etc. Here, we reflect on observations of mutual shaping
604 effects in our foundational works, specifically resulting from our teaching approach to robot automation.

605 During our first study, we observed evidence of mutual shaping and the teacher creating a mental model
606 of the robot. For example, our teacher realised with experience that children tended to have issues with some
607 aspect of the game (i.e., what food a dragonfly eats). Consequently, she changed her strategy to provide
608 additional examples and support for this aspect of the game. Similarly, the teacher also found that the
609 robot was not initiating some action often and consequently used some actions more frequently toward
610 the end of the teaching phase to ensure that the robot would exhibit enough of these actions. This exactly
611 evidences that notion that human teachers can tailor their teaching to a (robot) learner’s progress (Bloom,
612 1984; Thomaz and Breazeal, 2008)

613 In the second study, we were able to demonstrate mutual shaping in the way the fitness instructor used
614 the robot differently for different participants and/or at different stages of the C25K programme. The
615 longitudinal nature of this study, combined with our approach in supplementing the diadic robot-user
616 interactions with expert-user interactions, meant the fitness instructor got to know each user’s exercise
617 style/needs and could tailor the robot’s behaviour accordingly. This resulted in the autonomous robot
618 similarly producing behaviour that varied across participants. Similarly, as the programme progressed, the
619 fitness instructor could tailor the robot’s behaviour to reflect the changing exercise demands (e.g. using less
620 actions when the periods of running were longer). The flexibility of our approach was also demonstrated
621 when, in response to this increase in intensity, the fitness instructor requested we add a robot-led cool-down
622 period to the end of each exercise session. This was relatively simple to implement from a technical
623 perspective (an additional ‘walk’ instruction at the end of each session plan) but represented a new part of
624 the session for which there existed no previous training data. As we made this change within the teaching
625 phase (before the switch to autonomous operation) the instructor was able to address this, such that the robot
626 was able to successfully and appropriately support this new cool-down phase when running autonomously.

627 We also saw an interesting, emergent synergy in the way that the fitness instructor utilised and worked
628 alongside the robot coach. Towards the end of the study, as exercise sessions became more demanding,
629 the fitness instructor took more time at the end of each session to undertake stretching exercises with each
630 participant. This led to small amounts of overlap between each participant, at which point the fitness
631 instructor would start the next participant warming up with the robot, whilst he finished stretching with the
632 previous participant. We find this to be compelling evidence of the way domain experts will change their
633 practice and/or the way they utilise technological tools deployed into their workplace, particularly when

634 they can be confident in their expectations of how that technology will perform, as is particularly fostered
635 by our approach.

636 **4.4 IML for the Teaching Interaction: Opportunities and Limitations**

637 As noted previously, both of our foundational studies utilised IML via the SPARC paradigm to facilitate
638 the teaching interaction. From a technical perspective, our foundational studies demonstrate the feasibility
639 and relative effectiveness (in terms of teaching time) of this approach. Fundamentally, LEADOR is agnostic
640 with regards to the specific computational approach to facilitating the teaching interaction, but we find
641 IML to be a particularly compelling solution, in-line with the overall aims of the method, as it makes
642 for an intuitive bi-directional teaching interaction for the domain expert. Specifically, through one single
643 interface, they can see what the robot intends to do (and potentially why) before that action is executed,
644 improving their understanding of the robot's learning progress, and instantiate teaching exemplars in
645 real-time, informed by that understanding as well as the instantaneous requirements of the application task.

646 However, here we draw attention to one key limitation here regarding expert-robot interactions and
647 assessment when using IML. An important element of mutual shaping not considered here is if/how/to what
648 extent the suggestions made by the learning robots may have influenced the domain experts. For example,
649 had the learning robots not been making suggestions, such that the robot was entirely controlled/teleoperated
650 by the experts, would the action distribution and timing of actions remained the same? Further, if the
651 experts did not have the ability to actively reject suggestions (indicating that the learner was not producing
652 appropriate robot behaviour) would they still have post-hoc identified those actions as being inappropriate?

653 This is particularly interesting given the high number of suggested actions still being rejected at the end
654 of the training phase, in both of our foundational studies, immediately followed by seemingly appropriate
655 robot behaviour that was positively evaluated by the experts themselves during autonomous operation.
656 Success of our approach inherently assumes that the domain expert/system 'teacher' would provide a
657 'correct' and fairly consistent response; i.e. that they (i) can correctly assess the quality of each action
658 suggested by the robot and make an informed about whether this action should be executed and (ii) are
659 always able to ensure that required robot actions are executed in a timely fashion. With SPARC, these
660 robot suggestions are the main mean to help the expert create a mental model of the robot behaviour.
661 Consequently, whilst our results demonstrate the IML does fundamentally 'work' for automating robot
662 behaviour, and that our domain experts did construct a mental model of the robots' behaviour, there remains
663 an open question regarding how the robot could improve the transparency of its behaviour to actively
664 support mental model creation for the teacher.

5 DISCUSSION

665 **5.1 A Flexible and Effective Method for Automating Social Robots**

666 We suggest that LEADOR can be used to design robots for a variety of interaction settings, in terms of
667 the required autonomy and the nature of expert-robot-user interactions long-term. We propose two axes
668 to describe the different types of interaction that might be desired, based on the application (Figure 3).
669 A first axis describes the extent to which the domain expert(s) and user(s) are expected to interact long
670 term, as a supplement to the robot-user interaction(s). The second axis reflects the autonomy of the robot,
671 from full supervision (teleoperation) to full autonomy. These two axes are independent as, for example,
672 cases exist where the expert might be continuously interacting with the target users, while continuing or
673 not to supervise and/or improve the robot's autonomous behaviour long term. In addition, these axes do not
674 represent a discrete space, as the teaching interaction element of LEADOR specifically makes it possible to
675 move along either axis at any point during real world deployment.

Figure 3. Two dimensional representation for visualising the different types of long-term expert-robot-user interactions that a social robot might be designed for, all of which LEADOR can facilitate. Note this is not a discrete space, and LEADOR specifically makes it possible to move along these axes upon real-world deployment.

676 The robots developed in our foundational studies demonstrate this flexibility, and exist in slightly different
 677 spaces on these axes. Senft et al. (2019)'s educational robot is an example of an autonomous robot operating
 678 without the expert, and the teaching interaction represented a typical Wizard-of-Oz setup, i.e. there was
 679 no interaction. Winkle et al. (2020)'s robot fitness coach is closer to an autonomous robot operating
 680 side-by-side with the domain expert, and the teaching interaction utilised some interaction between the
 681 expert and the users (although this was undertaken *outside* of direct teleoperation).

682 The two foundational studies also demonstrate and evaluate different, complimentary elements of the
 683 effectiveness of LEADOR for designing social robots. More specifically, Senft et al. (2019) fundamentally
 684 demonstrated the practical feasibility of the teaching interaction for creating appropriate autonomous
 685 behaviour. After a teaching phase with 25 children, the robot was deployed autonomously and without
 686 expert supervision. It displayed a similar policy to when it was supervised, for example, capturing
 687 connections between some events and actions with appropriate timing. However, it was not using a PD
 688 approach from the onset, if LEADOR had been applied, teachers would have been involved more thoroughly
 689 in the game design and the interface development.

690 Whilst Winkle et al. (2020) again demonstrated similarity between supervised and autonomous behaviour,
691 this work also specifically demonstrated that the teaching interaction resulted in a better autonomous robot
692 than an expert-informed heuristic based alternative. In addition, the work specifically explored to what
693 extent the overall LEADOR could support mutual shaping and influence robot acceptability. To this end,
694 the significant co-design work undertaken by the domain expert seems likely to have contributed to the
695 high level of ownership he seemed to feel toward the system, and the way in which he conceptualised the
696 robot, throughout, as an independent agentic colleague he was training. When asked whether he perceived
697 Pepper as more of a tool or a colleague, the fitness instructor commented *“It was definitely more of a
698 colleague than a tool...I like to think her maybe early bugs or quirks definitely gave her a bit more of a
699 personality that maybe I held on to”*. In addition, when evaluating the robot’s performance, the instructor
700 also reflected on the difference between how the robot might behave in comparison to himself: *“Pepper’s
701 suggestions might not be what *I* would say in that exact same situation, however it doesn’t mean that
702 what was said or suggested was wrong”*. This gives credibility to the suggestion that LEADOR can be used
703 to create robots that do not simply attempt to imitate or replicate the domain expert directly, but instead
704 play a distinct but complimentary role alongside that domain expert in delivering an assistive intervention.

705 The fitness instructor’s feedback also suggested use of the robot did not prevent him from still developing
706 a working relationship with the exercisers, nor from having a positive impact on their motivation, as
707 he *“did care about their progress and their health”*. This appears to be true on the exerciser’s side too,
708 as their evaluations suggested they perceived the fitness instructor and the robot as playing distinct but
709 complimentary roles in their undertaking of and engagement with the prescribed exercise programme:
710 *“Pepper was a good instructor and positively motivated my runs. The role of Don [the fitness instructor]
711 assisted this in that having him there meant I could follow the robot’s instructions safe in the knowledge
712 that there was some support there should anything go wrong!”*

713 In summary, the fitness coach robot example therefore demonstrates the end-to-end PD element of
714 LEADOR, how this seemingly contributes to robot acceptability by both domain experts and target users,
715 and can successfully facilitate meaningful triadic (domain expert - robot - user) interactions in human-
716 centered domains where there might be a desire to reduce domain expert workload without ever removing
717 them from the interaction completely. As such, Winkle et al. (2020) might be seen as a first attempt to fully
718 implement LEADOR ahead of refinement for presentation as a generalisable methodology.

719 **5.2 Supporting ‘Responsible by Design’ Robotics**

720 The Foundation for Responsible Robotics (FRR) defines responsible robotics as ‘the responsible design,
721 development, use, implementation, and regulation of robotics in society’¹. Concerning research and
722 development, the FRR demonstrates significant overlap with the goals of mutual shaping, and hence our
723 goals in proposing LEADOR:

724 *“Responsible robotics starts before the robot has been constructed. Ethical decision-making begins in
725 the R&D phase. This includes the kind of research practices that are employed; ensuring that a diverse set
726 of viewpoints are represented in the development of the technology; using methods of development and
727 production that are sustainable; and taking into consideration the impact that the technology will have on
728 all stakeholders to mitigate harm preemptively rather than after the fact.”*

729 A significant number of attempts to more formally define the ethical design and development have taken
730 the form of published principles of AI and robotics², many of which similarly identify the importance of

¹ <https://responsiblerobotics.org/>

² <http://alanwinfield.blogspot.com/2019/04/an-updated-round-up-of-ethical.html>

731 engaging (non-roboticist) users and domain experts in robot design and evaluation processes. Arguably
732 one of the more practical resources is the British standard BS8611-2016 *Guide to the ethical design and*
733 *application of robots and robotic systems* (BSI, 2016), which explicitly identifies ethical risks posed by
734 robots, mitigating strategies and suggested methods for verification and validation. Notably, the standard
735 suggests that a number of the identified ethical hazards might be verified and validated through *expert*
736 *guidance* and *user validation*. Through LEADOR, such guidance and validation is inherently ‘built-in’
737 to the design and development process. Based on this, we posit that, in supporting a mutual shaping
738 approach to robot development, and specifically by ‘opening up’ robot automation to non-roboticists (such
739 that they can contribute to robot design and automation, but also better understand robot capabilities and
740 limitations) LEADOR also represents a concrete implementation of a *responsible robotics* approach, and
741 offers a practical way to create social robots with expert guidance and user validation being inherent to the
742 development process. Consequently, while the program is evaluated by its designers, these designers are
743 the domain experts and thus the best persons to assess whether the robot behaviour is successful or not.

744 5.3 Future Development

745 5.3.1 Inclusion of Application Targets in Design, Automation and Evaluation

746 A key limitation in both of our foundational works was the lack of including target users during the
747 design processes. This is partly because both of these works concerned the development of robots that
748 would be assisting the domain expert practitioners (i.e. a teaching assistant and a fitness instructor), and so
749 it made sense to focus on working with such experts as co-designers of the system. However, as discussed
750 in the introduction, inclusion of all stakeholders is a key aim of mutual shaping approaches to robot
751 design/development.

752 A desire to include target users in the robot’s design and evaluation would raise the interesting question of
753 how target users, who are expecting to be beneficiaries of the interaction, could design the robot. In a number
754 of situations where the robot is expected to provide support or additional knowledge, including target users
755 in the co-design of the action state for example could be either complex or negate the *perception* of the
756 robot as an agent. This also overlaps with discussions in contemporary PD works regarding the ‘legitimacy’
757 of different PD participants, and specifically with the idea of participants *learning* from the researchers as
758 a pre-requisite for becoming such (Ehn, 2008). In the first instance however, as an obvious extension to
759 LEADOR, target users could certainly be included in preliminary testing of those actions designed with a
760 domain expert.

761 5.3.2 Alternative Teaching/Learning Interactions

762 The method presented in this paper focused on a teaching phase where a domain expert teaches the robot
763 how to interact with a target user, with the target user unaware of the extent to which the expert is involved
764 in the robot behaviour. It abstracts away the type of learning used as each situation has different constraints
765 and requires variations on the teaching interaction and learning algorithm. Consequently, LEADOR might
766 not be applicable directly to every situation. Future work should explore the applicability of LEADOR
767 with other interaction designs not explored in our foundational studies, and explore combination with other
768 methodologies to extend this applicability whilst maintaining the key tenets regarding expert-involvement
769 and in-situ robot design, teaching and testing.

770 While situations such as therapy or education require the expert and target user to be different persons,
771 a large number of other domain relaxes this constraint. For example, an elderly at home could have a
772 robot carer, and teach the robot how to support them in their daily activity. In this case, the target user is
773 the person knowing best their needs and as such would be the perfect expert. LEADOR would be highly
774 applicable to this situation as the target users could be involved early in the design process, help specify the

775 state and action spaces and tools they would need and finally teach in situ their robot how to interact while
776 benefiting from the interaction themselves.

777 Alternatively, building on the previously noted limitation regarding target user inclusion, applications
778 where the robot is to play more of a *peer* role, rather than an expert authority might be best achieved by
779 having one target user teach the robot how to interact with another target user. This might be particularly
780 appropriate for e.g. allowing teenagers to automate companion robots that supporting teenagers' mental
781 health Björling and Rose (2019). This raises a number of interesting research questions regarding how
782 the teaching interaction might impact on the teacher's (self-)understanding of the application domain,
783 representing another aspect of mutual shaping that could be considered in more detail in future works.

784 An alternative, exciting teaching interaction is having the teaching phase being open and transparent to the
785 target user. Teaching robots could be similar to how adults teach children to interact, by providing explicit
786 feedback guidelines openly in the social environment. This situation raises a number of open questions such
787 as to what extent having the expert providing feedback to the robot could impact the ascribed agency of the
788 robot, or how could the target user be included in telling the robot how best to help them. We have good
789 evidence from our work Winkle et al. (2020) that such open interaction would not 'break the illusion' of the
790 robot being an independent (credible) social agent. Further, previous work suggests that robot users value
791 the human developers 'behind' the robot, as it is their 'genuine intentions' that underlie the robot's social
792 and assistive behaviours Winkle et al. (2019b). In sensitive application environments such as the previously
793 mentioned teenage mental health support, such openness may indeed be crucial to robot effectiveness and
794 acceptability Björling et al. (2020).

795 However, these alternative teacher/learner configurations need to account for the existing practical
796 constraints of using reinforcement learning (RL) in human robot interaction. Indeed, in the context of
797 human-robot interaction, RL faces two main issues, (1) the large number of datapoints required to improve
798 the policy (which have to come from real world interaction) and (2) the risks posed by the RL 'exploration'
799 in the real human-robot interaction, where the RL algorithm might suggest actions that are inappropriate in
800 a given context.

801 In our two studies, the domain expert also acted as a 'gate keeper' for the robot's suggestions, and as a
802 general safety net, able to intervene if the autonomous robot behaviour was inappropriate. Likewise, when
803 applying LEADOR in other scenarios, adequate safeguarding needs to be in place, until further research on
804 reinforcement learning can provide adequate safety guarantees. Alternatively, the expert could serve early
805 on to help create an initial safe and effective policy by providing a high amount of guidance. Then, in a
806 second phase, the expert could revert only to the 'gate keeper' role, working as a safeguard to ensure that
807 the robot's policy has a minimum efficacy, while letting the robot self-improve. Finally, when the robot
808 reaches a sufficient expertise in the interaction, it could be left to fine tune its policy with less supervision.

6 CONCLUSION

809 In this article we present *Led-by-Experts Automation and Design Of Robots* (LEADOR), a method for end-
810 to-end participatory design (PD) of autonomous social robots that supports a mutual shaping approach to
811 social robotics. This general method is derived from two, independent foundational studies and represents a
812 culmination of the authors' experiences of working with domain experts in the development of autonomous
813 socially assistive robots. We describe the activities undertaken in those studies to demonstrate how the
814 method has been derived and give tangible examples of how it might be applied. Together, we suggest these
815 foundational studies also demonstrate both the feasibility and the value of the approach, as both resulted in

816 acceptable, autonomous and effective socially assistive robots successfully utilised in complex real world
817 environments.

818 The first key contribution of LEADOR is to make robot *automation* participatory, such that non-roboticist,
819 domain experts can contribute directly to generating autonomous robot behaviours. This particularity
820 compliments more typical use of PD for e.g. generating initial robot design guidelines or evaluation robot
821 prototypes. We achieve this expert-led automation by utilising a *teaching interaction*, whereby the domain
822 expert(s) can directly define and refine the robot's autonomous behaviour through a teaching interface. Both
823 of our foundational studies utilised interactive machine learning and the SPARC paradigm (Senft et al.,
824 2015) which we suggest is particularly well suited to the overall method goals, therefore we particularly
825 reflect on this approach and its benefits, challenges and limitations. However, whilst we refer to this as a
826 teaching interaction, as the domain expert is 'teaching' the robot how to behave, our method is agnostic as
827 to the specific technical approach taken (e.g. machine learning, authoring) to facilitate it.

828 The second key contribution of our LEADOR is to facilitate a mutual shaping approach throughout robot
829 development. This is achieved, firstly, by the increased domain expert participation in robot automation
830 as described above. In addition however, our integration of the teaching interaction into real world robot
831 deployment means that this automation of robot behaviour can actually be informed by and reflect the
832 complex and nuanced realities of the real world context, capturing the expert's tacit and intuitive responses
833 to real-world social dynamics. Given that teaching can be re-convened at anytime, the method also facilitates
834 the updating of robot behaviours in response to these dynamics evolving, or new dynamics emerging, i.e.
835 observation of mutual shaping effects. More generally, the in-situ robot deployment and expert teaching
836 role maximises the opportunity to identify and understand such mutual shaping effects to better evaluate
837 the robot's overall impact and efficacy for the proposed application.

838 In facilitating end-to-end PD and mutual shaping, we also suggest our method inherently supports
839 responsible robotics, by design. Specifically, it allows for a diverse set of viewpoints to be represented in
840 the development of the technology, and for preemptive consideration of the impact that technology will
841 have on stakeholders. Finally, on a practical level, we also suggest our method can better facilitate multi-
842 disciplinary working as it systematically combines participatory design and technical development such
843 that non-roboticist researchers and stakeholders are no longer excluded from any stage of the development
844 process.

845 In summary, we suggest LEADOR is an all-around effective approach for creating socially intelligent
846 robots, as *practical* as it is *responsible* in facilitating the creation of expert-informed, intuitive social
847 behaviours. We identify a number of areas for potential future development, which we hope will be of
848 interest to other roboticists in refining the method further, and working further towards democratisation of
849 robot design and development.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

850 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
851 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

852 KW and ES led foundational studies 1 and 2 from which this work is derived, both of which were
853 (independently) conducted in close collaboration with SL. KW and ES led on derivation of the generalisable
854 method based on their shared experiences, with all authors contributing to reflections on the foundational
855 studies, resultant implications for the generalisable methodology and producing the final manuscript.

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Figure 4. Pictorial representations of the participatory design activities and final teaching setup undertaken in application of our method to Winkle et al. (2020)'s robot fitness coach, as per Table 2 with reference to Steps 1-5 of our method as per Figure 1.